

Impact Study

Economic Activity & Industrial Applications

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Context

Biodata resources hold significant potential to spur economic growth: they hold a wealth of scientific data that can and has been used in the development of new products, technologies and services. By leveraging these repositories, businesses and researchers can accelerate innovation, reduce development costs and create novel solutions to complex challenges. This synergy between biodata resources and industry not only drives scientific progress but also opens up new avenues for economic expansion and competitiveness.

This series of case studies explores how biodata resources have practically contributed to enhancing economic activity and supported development across diverse industries.

Driving antibody innovation

Antibodies are proteins that help in neutralising disease through binding with an invader's antigens. The [Human Protein Atlas](#) is dedicated to providing access to the whole human proteome – the set of proteins which make up an organism. Researchers from the Human Protein Atlas project founded Swedish Life Science company [Atlas Antibodies](#) in 2006, to directly use data and insights gathered in this resource as a scientific foundation to advance our understanding of the human proteome. The company [highlights](#) how data and insights gathered through the Human Protein Atlas project have been providing a robust scientific basis for their product development.

Today, Atlas Antibodies manufactures over 22,000 primary antibodies targeting a wide spectrum of human proteins relevant to diverse applications. In recent years, Atlas Antibodies has grown significantly, thanks to their cutting-edge work and the ability to capitalise on the Human Protein Atlas. In 2021, the company [nearly tripled in size](#) (from revenue of 128 million SEK in 2020 to 324 million SEK in 2021), and has been growing its capabilities through strategic acquisitions across Europe.

Another organisation driving innovation in the antibody space is the Oxford Protein Informatics Group (OPIG), which has developed a series of computational tools to support the reduction of costs and the acceleration of the discovery and development of antibody therapeutics. Their free tools are available online, including [SAbDab](#) and [SAbPred](#). SAbDab is a database containing all the antibody structures available in the [Protein Data Bank](#), which have been annotated and presented in a consistent fashion, whereas SAbPred is a server that hosts antibody computational prediction tools and has been developed in collaboration with UCB, Medimmune, AstraZeneca, and Roche under an [open-innovation agreement](#). These tools are complemented by the broader package [SAbBox](#), which groups them in the form of a virtual machine for easier use; SAbBox is available for free for academic use as well as through commercial licensing.

As of 2020, the SAbDab-SAbPred suite had been used by [over 100](#) pharmaceutical companies. Nine pharmaceutical companies (GSK, UCB, Roche, AstraZeneca, Lonza, Iontas, Kymab, Tikcro and Agenus Bio) were reported to have custom installations of the SAbDab-SAbPred suite, whereas five had purchased SAbBox licences (GlaxoSmithKline plc (GSK), Kotai Biotech, Gritstone Oncology, Cenmed Enterprise and Dragonfly Therapeutics).

These companies have been able to develop new therapeutics faster and more accurately than previous tools would otherwise allow, and with reduced costs. In the case of GSK, they highlighted that the SAbBox software “reduces the cost of development by an estimated £500,000 to £2,000,000 in wet work [experiments] and FTE [staff] per campaign.” Similarly, Voyager Therapeutics, a Boston-based biotechnology company, was able to replace their commercial tools with tools from SAbPred, making a saving of more than \$100,000 per antibody.

Enabling new product development

[miRBase](#) is a searchable database of published MicroRNA sequences and annotations, managed by researchers from the University of Manchester in the UK. [MicroRNAs](#) are a class of RNA genes that regulate the expression of protein coding mRNAs in animals and plants.

miRBase data enables the production of experimental kits, resources and tools by companies such as ABI, Invitrogen, Sigma-Aldrich and Exiqon. The tools created by these companies have now been used in academic and industrial settings to enable drug discovery, product development and use in clinical research.

Exiqon, for example, sells [20](#) different products that have relied on sequence data sourced from miRBase for their development. These products are important for Exiqon's revenue streams and continued economic growth. Their Vice President for Research and Development stated, "From interaction with our customers we understand that everyone in the miRNA research community consider the miRNA content of miRBase to represent the golden standard miRNA repository. Over the years, Exiqon has used miRBase as a reference for further development of new products and updating of existing products."

Data from miRBase is also being used in a clinical setting, as microRNA can play a prominent role in understanding disease prognosis and improving the performance of drugs. [TargetScan](#), which predicts miRNA gene targets, includes almost all identified miRNA sequences reported in miRBase, and supports the analysis of sequence data. Meanwhile, miRagen Therapeutics (now [Viridian Therapeutics](#)) has used microRNA from miRBase to support the development of therapies and drugs for chronic heart failure and cardiometabolic disease.

Three cheers for biodata resources

As health and nutrition company [DSM](#) discovered in the early 2000s, proline-specific endoproteases can play an important role in the context of beer production. This type of protease, an enzyme that breaks down proteins into smaller polypeptides or single amino acids, was found to [help with the reduction or prevention of haze](#) – the cloudy or turbid appearance of the beverage, as opposed to a clear and translucent look that is often found to be more appealing by consumers. DSM researchers also unexpectedly found that the endoprotease they discovered can help reduce gluten in the context of the beer brewing process, which was recognised as a significant commercial opportunity. The novelty of their discovery was confirmed using BLAST searches of databases such as [SwissProt](#) (now part of the Universal Protein Resource Consortium, UniProt), the [Protein Information Resource \(PIR\)](#) and trEMBL (now also part of UniProt), which compared the coding sequence of the discovered *Aspergillus niger* derived proline specific endoprotease to records in these databases.

These discoveries are what led DSM to commercialising this endoprotease as Brewers Clarex, which was originally designed to prevent the formation of chill haze in beer by breaking down haze-causing proteins. Its unexpected gluten-reducing properties are leveraged to create [gluten-reduced beers](#) that can be consumed by many gluten-sensitive individuals. [Over 30](#) breweries across Europe and the USA are using Brewers Clarex to develop gluten-reduced beers for the growing gluten-free beverage market, which was worth [\\$2.5 billion](#) in 2023 and projected to reach \$4billion by 2030.

Conclusions

The case studies presented in this series demonstrate the significant impact of biodata resources on driving economic growth and innovation, including through distinct pathways such as direct data (re)use and software solutions built around biodata resources. These developments show not only scientific progress but also avenues for economic growth and new market creation.

What is perhaps most interesting is that the funding required to create and maintain the resources mentioned in these case studies is significantly smaller than the economic and social value they have enabled across just a small selection of examples. This remarkable return on investment highlights the critical importance of sustained funding for biodata resources: even modest expenditure in developing and maintaining high-quality, openly accessible biodata can unleash a wave of scientific and economic advances that pay dividends many times over.

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Appendix – Resources discussed

Resources	About
Blast	The Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST) finds regions of local similarity between sequences and is available on the web on the NCBI website. The program compares nucleotide or protein sequences to sequence databases and calculates the statistical significance of matches. BLAST can be used to infer functional and evolutionary relationships between sequences as well as help identify members of gene families. BLASTp, or Protein BLAST, is used to compare protein sequences. Users can input one or more protein sequences that they want to compare against a single protein sequence or a database of protein sequences.
ChEMBL	ChEMBL is a manually curated online database of bioactive small molecules which exhibit drug-like properties, further supported by three thematic portals designed for users with a particular research focus. ChEMBL is provided by the EMBL's European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI).
Human Protein Atlas	The Human Protein Atlas provides data across 12 distinct aspects of the genome-wide analysis of human proteins, supporting the exploration of the human proteome in detail. The Swedish-based programme commenced in 2003, supports scientists in academic and industry and has been cited in approaching 900 research publications.
Protein Data bank	<p>The Protein Data Bank (PDB) was established as the first open access digital data resource in all of biology and medicine. It is today a leading global resource for experimental data central to scientific discovery.</p> <p>Through an internet information portal and downloadable data archive, PDB provides access to 3D structure data for the molecules of life, found in all organisms on the planet.</p>
SAbDab, SAbPred & SAbBox	The tools in the SAbDab-SAbPred platform are open access and comprise an online database of consistently annotated antibody structures covering all antibodies in the Protein Data Bank (SAbDab), alongside online antibody prediction tools (SAbPred). The tools were created by the Oxford Protein Informatics Group (OPIG) and have been unified in SAbBox, a virtual machine solution that is available for academic and commercial use.

Global Biodata Coalition

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